

Species 1: *H. melpomene***NOT test****Species 2: *H. hecale***

PC1, PNT.index: 0.81; high PNT

PC1, PNT.index: 0.65; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.224

EquivalencyNiche Similarity:
D = 0.514D
p.value = 0.19361**Background 2→1**D
p.value = 0.00334**Background 1→2**D
p.value = 0.0025

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. hecale*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.524$

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

